

VARIATIONAL ANALYSIS OF FIBER QUALITY INDICATORS IN G3 HYBRID FAMILIES UNDER MODERATELY SALINE SOIL AND CLIMATIC CONDITIONS OF KARAKALPAKSTAN

R.M. Zholymbetova¹, U.E. Aytjanov², B.U. Aytjanov³

PhD student, Karakalpakstan Institute of Agriculture and Agrotechnologies¹

Doctor of Agricultural Sciences, Senior Researcher Head of Laboratory, Karakalpakstan Research
Institute of Agriculture²

Doctor of Agricultural Sciences, Senior Researcher Head of Laboratory, Grains and Rice Scientific
Production Association³

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15478752>

Abstract. *One of the most urgent tasks in cotton growing today is the creation of new cotton varieties that are adapted to the regional soil-climatic conditions, resistant to soil salinity, early-maturing, disease- and pest-resistant, high-yielding, and meet global standards for fiber quality. The growth of cotton and other crops under saline soil conditions, as well as the exchange of substances and other processes in them, negatively affect the quality of the products obtained. This is because the plant's nutrition becomes more difficult due to changes in the soil caused by various biochemical processes. Therefore, in this article, ecological-geographical long-term samples, local varieties, and G3 hybrid families were studied in terms of fiber length, micronaire index, relative break strength, spinning coefficient, dominance (hp) level, and how the fiber quality meets global standards.*

Keywords: *cotton hybridization, hybrid combinations, fiber quality, micronaire, spinning ability, relative break strength, inch, dominance coefficient, heterosis, ecological-geographical.*

INTRODUCTION. In cotton cultivation, one of the most pressing tasks today is the creation of new cotton varieties that are adapted to regional soil-climatic conditions, resistant to soil salinity, early-maturing, disease- and pest-resistant, high-yielding, and meet global standards for fiber quality. The growth of cotton and other crops under saline soil conditions, as well as the exchange of substances and other processes within them, negatively affect the quality of the products obtained. This is because the plant's nutrition becomes difficult due to changes in the soil caused by various biochemical processes. Therefore, in this article, ecological-geographical long-term samples, local varieties, and G3 hybrid families were studied in terms of fiber length, micronaire index, relative break strength, spinning coefficient, dominance (hp) level, and how the fiber quality meets global standards.

According to the United Nations data, due to soil degradation in agricultural lands, more than 1.5 billion people around the world are facing severe food shortages. According to global maps, saline soils in agricultural lands cover 833.0 million hectares, which accounts for 8.7% of our planet's surface. In our country, irrigated land amounts to 4.3 million hectares, 44.7% of which is salinized to varying degrees: 31.0% slightly salinized, 11.9% moderately salinized, and 1.9% strongly salinized. It is known that in slightly salinized soils, crop yields decrease by 10-20%, in moderately salinized soils by 20-50%, and in strongly salinized soils by 50-80%. It should be emphasized that the study of cotton samples brought from the origin centers of cotton, crossbred with local varieties under the medium salinity soil-climatic conditions of Karakalpakstan, is an urgent issue for creating starting materials for selection based on analyzing valuable agricultural traits of the generations, in order to create varieties that are tolerant to various extreme conditions and produce high-quality and high-yielding crops in

saline soils.

Research by scientists shows that it is possible to conduct effective selective breeding without performing individual selection in the initial stages of hybrid populations. This method, particularly for creating varieties that are geographically distant, have large bolls, high fiber yield, and quality, has been proven to be highly effective.

In the recommendations of A. B. Amanaturdiev and others, the use of modern innovative technology to determine fiber quality is proposed. According to the Uster HVI classification system, fiber's spinning ability coefficient is divided into five categories: C (below 120), B (120-129), A (130-140), A+ (140-149), and A++ (above 150). Therefore, when the spinning ability coefficient of fiber is 150 or higher, the quality of the fiber is also rated highly. This approach, suggested by scientists, will help save labor resources and time, and most importantly, increase the precision of analyses, thereby ensuring the genetic purity of the variety and ultimately leading to a significant increase in cotton yield.

According to the research of K. O. Khudarganov, S. A. Usmanov, S. S. Alikhodjaeva, and M. M. Abdullaev, factors such as the reduction of arable land and global climate change are increasing the demand for salt-tolerant cotton varieties, similar to other agricultural crop varieties. To address these issues, the creation of salt-tolerant, fast-maturing, high-yielding varieties that meet the international market standards for fiber quality has become a priority. In this regard, scientists of the PSUAEITI's "Water Scarcity and Salt-Tolerant Cotton Varieties Selection" laboratory have recommended using the cotton variety SP-7702, which is classified as Type IV with high opening speed, high fiber yield and quality (in terms of micronaire, fiber length, relative break strength, and fiber uniformity), as the starting material for research in genetics and selection.

METHODS OF CONDUCTING THE EXPERIMENT. The scientific research was conducted in the field and laboratory conditions of the Karakalpakstan Scientific Research Institute of Agriculture [1; 2]. The institute is located 4 km northeast of the city of Chimbay, at 43°–44° north latitude, in the territory of Chimbay district, Republic of Karakalpakstan. The soil in the experimental field is moderately saline in mechanical composition, with groundwater located at a depth of 1.5–2.0 meters. Summers are mostly cloudless, and the annual precipitation is 150–160 mm. The soil surface usually begins to thaw in March.

Under field conditions, seeds were sown in a 60 × 25 × 1 arrangement at a depth of 3–5 cm, using three replications, with 50 planting holes per replication, and 3–4 seeds were placed in each hole. After the harvest, the laboratory studies were aimed at examining foreign and local cotton varieties and F₃ generation hybrids. The goal was to develop early-ripening, high-yielding initial breeding materials with type IV fiber, suitable for practical selection, by hybridizing local varieties with accessions from China, Africa, Australia, India, Pakistan, and the USA under the moderately saline soil and climatic conditions of Karakalpakstan.

Among the samples, F₃ generation hybrids, parent lines, and the standard variety S-4727 were sown. All field observations were carried out following standard experimental procedures. Specifically, phenological observations were conducted based on morphobiological traits, and valuable economic traits were analyzed in both field and laboratory conditions. The results obtained from the experiments were statistically processed according to the method of B.A. Dospekhov [4]. Each trait's indicators were mathematically analyzed; differences between varieties and hybrids were assessed using the Fisher criterion (F), general experimental error (S_x), error of mean differences (S_d), and the Least Significant Difference (LSD) at a 95% confidence level.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND THEIR DISCUSSION. According to the studies conducted by E. Rakhmatkhojaeva et al. [6], the fiber quality indicators of the lines created as a result of wide eco-geographical hybridization of cotton were analyzed based on characteristics such as spinning consistency index (SCI), micronaire value (Mic), fiber length (Lend, inches), specific breaking strength (Str, g/tex), and uniformity index (UI, %). Based on these analyses, F₃ hybrid plants obtained by crossing local varieties with each other and with the African G. stocksii Mast. specimen, produced new lines with type IV fiber. These lines were selected for further development as initial breeding materials that could incorporate other valuable agronomic traits in subsequent years.

In the Republic's "Sifat" (Quality) Center, cotton and its related products are classified according to international standards. To classify cotton fiber at the Universal Standard level, specific criteria and standards have been developed, and a classer school has been established at the Center. This school operates in accordance with international exchange requirements and trains specialists for both cotton-producing and consuming countries.

The micronaire (Mic) value reflects the fineness and maturity of the cotton fiber based on its air permeability. According to local literature, Mic values are categorized as follows: below 3.0 – "very fine"; 3.0–3.9 – "fine"; 4.0–4.9 – "medium"; 5.0–5.9 – "coarse"; and above 6.0 – "very coarse." In the Republic of Uzbekistan, for the I and II industrial grades of raw cotton, the acceptable range of micronaire values is specified to be between 3.5 and 4.9. These values are officially stated in purchasing documentation as limit indicators.

In the research, quality indicators such as the spinning consistency index (SCI), micronaire (Mic), fiber length (inches), specific breaking strength (Str, g/tex), and fiber uniformity (UI, %) were analyzed for samples obtained from foreign varieties, local varieties, F₃ hybrid lines, and the standard variety S-4727. The fiber quality traits were determined at the "Sifat" certification center using modern HVI (High Volume Instrument) measurement equipment.

Micronaire value and spinning consistency index analysis under moderately saline soil and climatic conditions of Karakalpakstan.

Under the moderately saline soil and climatic conditions of Karakalpakstan, the micronaire values of cotton fiber from foreign varieties, samples, local varieties, and F₃ hybrid families were mathematically analyzed by constructing variation series. Based on this, plants from parental forms and hybrid families were grouped into eight classes ($K = 2 \text{ Mic}$) ranging from 3.7 to 5.2 Mic. Among the foreign samples, the average micronaire values ranged from 4.4 to 4.7, while in local varieties they ranged from 4.3 in the KK-3535 variety to 4.6 in the Sulton variety. For F₃ hybrid families, the average values ranged from 4.3 to 4.6, and the standard variety S-4727 had a value of 4.8.

In parental forms, including ecologically and geographically distant foreign and local varieties, the majority of plants (66.6% in 06201 – Africa and up to 87.5% in 06058 – China) fell into classes 3 to 6 (Mic range 4.1–4.8). Among the F₃ hybrids, 72.7% of plants in the F₃ (Pakistan. 07291×KK-3535) combination and up to 87.5% in the F₃ (Australia. 06830×Chimboy-5018) combination also fell within these classes.

The coefficient of variation in micronaire value ranged from 5.9–7.7% in parental forms and 5.5–7.2% in F₃ hybrids (Table 1). Research results showed that under Karakalpakstan's moderately saline conditions, the micronaire values in F₃ hybrids were generally higher than those of their parental lines. A large number of plants were found within classes 2 to 5 (Mic range 3.9–4.6) among the hybrids.

Currently, the spinning consistency index (SCI) of cotton fiber is receiving increased attention from cotton agro-clusters. SCI, which reflects the fiber's spinning performance, is determined based on the length and strength modules. The index is categorized as follows: above 150 – very high; 140–149 – high; 130–139 – medium; 120–129 – low; and below 120 – very low.

1-table

Variation Analysis of the Micronaire (Mic) Trait in F₃ Hybrid Cotton Families Under Moderately Saline Soil Conditions of Karakalpakstan

№	Parental Forms and F ₃ Hybrid Families	K=2 mic.									n	M±m	Δ	V%
		3,7-3,8	3,9-4,0	4,1-4,2	4,3-4,4	4,5-4,6	4,7-4,8	4,9-5,0	5,1-5,2					
1.	(China) 06058	1	1	2	2	8	2				16	4,4±6,8	0,3	6,1
2.	(Africa) 06201		1	1	1	3	5	3	1		15	4,7±7,9	0,3	6,6
3.	(Australia) 06830	1	1	1	2	5	3	1			14	4,5±8,6	0,3	7,2
4.	(Australia) 09801		2	2	3	6	1	1	1		16	4,4±8,6	0,3	7,7
5.	(Pakistan) 07291		1	1	2	7	2	1	1		15	4,6±7,7	0,3	6,5
6.	(USA) 011571	1	1	2	6	2	1	1			14	4,4±8,2	0,3	7,0
7.	KK-3535	1	2	2	7	3	2				17	4,3±6,5	0,3	6,2
8.	Chimbay-5018		1	2	6	3	2	1			15	4,4±6,8	0,3	5,9
9.	Sultan			1	2	5	3	2	1		14	4,6±7,3	0,3	5,9
10.	F ₃ (China. 06058 x KK-3535)	2	3	3	6	5	2				21	4,3±6,7	0,3	7,1
11.	F ₃ (Africa. 06201 x Chimbay-5018)		1	1	2	7	4	3	1		19	4,6±4,5	0,3	6,1
12.	F ₃ (Australia. 06830 x Chimbay-5018)	1	2	3	12	4	2				24	4,3±4,8	0,2	5,5
13.	F ₃ (Australia. 09801 x KK-3535)	2	4	4	7	3	3				23	4,3±6,5	0,3	7,2
14.	F ₃ (Pakistan. 07291 x KK-3535)		1	1	3	8	4	4	1		22	4,6±6,0	0,3	6,1
15.	F ₃ (USA. 011571 x Sultan)	2	3	3	10	5	1				24	4,3±5,6	0,3	6,4
	St. C-4727			1	1	2	6	3	2		15	4,8±6,9	0,3	5,6

2-table

Variation Analysis of the Spinning Consistency Index (SCI) Trait in F₃ Hybrid Families Derived from Crosses Involving Foreign Varieties, Accessions, and Local Cotton Varieties

№	Parent Forms and F ₃ Hybrid Families	K=10 sci.							n	M±m	Δ	V%
		121-130	131-140	131-135	141-150	151-160	161-170	171-180				
1.	(China) 06058		1	3	6	3	2	1	16	149,1±3,4	13,7	9,1
2.	(Africa) 06201	1	2	7	3	1	1		15	138,9±3,4	1,3,3	9,6
3.	(Australia) 06830			2	7	2	2	1	14	150,9±3,4	12,9	8,5
4.	(Australia) 09801		1	1	4	8	2		16	152,2±2,4	9,8	6,4
5.	(Pakistan) 07291	2	2	3	5	2	1		15	139,7±4,0	15,6	11,1
6.	(USA) 011571		2	2	6	2	1	1	14	146,8±4,1	15,6	10,6
7.	KK-3535	1	3	3	8	1	1		17	141,3±3,2	13,2	9,3
8.	Chimbay-5018		2	2	7	3	1		15	145,2±3,1	12,2	8,4
9.	Sultan	1	2	3	6	2			14	140,6±3,1	11,8	8,4
10.	F ₃ (China. 06058 x KK-3535)		1	3	4	7	4	2	21	153,7±2,9	13,4	8,7
11.	F ₃ (Africa. 06201 x Chimbay-5018)	1	4	7	3	3	1		19	139,5±3,0	13,3	9,5
12.	F ₃ (Australia. 06830 x Chimbay-5018)		1	2	10	6	4	1	24	151,3±2,4	11,9	7,9
13.	F ₃ (Australia. 09801 x KK-3535)		2	3	10	5	3		23	147,2±2,4	11,7	7,9
14.	F ₃ (Pakistan. 07291 x KK-3535)	1	3	10	5	2	1		22	139,0±2,5	11,8	8,5
15.	F ₃ (USA. 011571 x Sultan)			2	4	11	6	1	24	155,9±2,1	10,6	6,8
	St. C-4727	2	3	6	3	1			15	134,4±3,2	12,4	9,2

In this study, variation analysis of SCI was conducted for F₃ hybrid families derived from foreign, local, and hybrid combinations under the soil and climate conditions of Karakalpakstan. The SCI values ranged from 121 to 180, distributed into seven classes (K = 10) (Table 3). In foreign sample families, SCI values ranged from an average of 138.9 in 06201 (Africa) to 152.2 in 09801 (Australia). In local varieties, it ranged from 140.6 in the Sultan variety to 145.2 in Chimboy-5018. Most plants were found in classes 3 to 5 (SCI range 131–160), with 71.4–81.2% of foreign samples and 70.5–80.0% of local varieties falling within this range. The standard variety S-4727 had an SCI value of 134.4.

According to the variation analysis, up to 21.4% of plants among the foreign, local, and hybrid varieties had SCI values above 161. The results indicated that F₃ hybrid families showed relatively higher spinning consistency index values compared to their parental lines, suggesting a favorable outcome.

CONCLUSION. Based on the results of the above research, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. According to the analysis of fiber quality traits, particularly the spinning coefficient, in the hybrids studied in the experiments, under the moderately saline soil and climatic conditions of Karakalpakstan, families located on the left side of the variation range were eliminated, while those on the right side of the range were selected as promising.

2. As a result of evaluating F₁–F₂–F₃ hybrid generations obtained from the involvement of foreign varieties, samples, and local cultivars, and through various selection methods, new families were identified that are adapted to the moderately saline soil and climatic conditions of Karakalpakstan. Specifically, 4 new families were identified from the combination F₃ (China. 06058 × KK-3535), 5 from F₃ (Australia. 06830 × Chimboy-5018), 3 from F₃ (Australia. 09801 × KK-3535), and 4 from F₃ (USA. 011571 × Sulton).

3. These families were characterized by early maturity (107–111 days), a high number of bolls (14–15 per plant), high single boll weight (5.8–6.2 g), high plant productivity (over 100 grams per plant), high fiber yield (38–40%), and a fiber index (7.6–8.4 g). Based on fiber quality indicators, they belong to Type IV and are recommended as new initial breeding material for cotton breeders.

REFERENCES

1. Aytjanov U.E., Aytjanov B.U., Sagatdinov I.J. Study of mutant breaker varieties according to the basic economic-valuable signs under the conditions of Karakalpakstan. // EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD), Volume 5, Issue 5, May 2020, pp. 135–137.
2. Aytjanov U.E., Aytjanov B.U., Sagatdinov I.J. Creation of new salt-, drought-, and wilt-resistant mutant varieties of medium fiber cotton with fiber yield over 40% and fiber quality of Type IV, and their transfer for study into the primer. // Journal of Critical Reviews, ISSN 2394-5125, Vol. 7, Issue 08, 2020, pp. 2121–2131.
3. Amanturdiyev A.B., Alihodjaeva S.S., Kuchkarov O.E. Cotton variety “S-5707”. In: Prospects for the Development of Cotton Growing in Uzbekistan. Tashkent, 2014, pp. 105–106.
4. Dospekhov B.A. Methodology of Field Experiments. Moscow: "Agropromizdat", 1985, p. 251.
5. Rakhmatkhodjaeva E., Ibragimov P., Urazov B., Ergasheva S. Fiber quality indicators of systems created by ecogeographically distant hybridization of cotton. // Journal: Agriculture and Water Management of Uzbekistan, Tashkent, No. 8, 2024, pp. 32–34.
6. Khudarganov K.O., Usmanov S.A., Alihodjaeva S.S., Abdullaeva M.M. Formation of some quantitative trait indicators in the new medium-fiber cotton variety “SP-7702”. // Agro Ilm Journal, No. 5 (68), 2020, pp. 5–6.